

Effect of the Dominant Pattern of Leadership on the Nature of the Work of Administrative Staff at Al-Aqsa University

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Abstract: *The objective of the study is to identify the effect of the dominant pattern of leadership on the nature of the work of administrative staff at Al-Aqsa University- Gaza. The researchers used the stratified random sample method in the study. The study was conducted on a sample of (99) administrative staff and the response rate was (80.80%).*

The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a moderate degree of the dominant pattern of leadership at Al-Aqsa University from the point of view of the administrative staff. The percentage reached (62.93%). And that there was an average level of satisfaction with the Nature of the work from the point of view of administrative staff, with percentage (64.60%). There is a direct correlation between The dominant pattern of leadership and the Nature of the work, a statistically significant effect of The dominant pattern of leadership on the Nature of the work, the absence of differences between the sample in the view of the type of leadership and the Nature of the work depending on the gender variable, the absence of differences in the perception of The dominant pattern of leadership and Nature of the work depending on the age variable. That there are no statistically significant differences in the perception of the type of leadership and the Nature of the work according to the variable of scientific qualification, the absence of differences in perception of The dominant pattern of leadership depending on the variable years of service, the existence of differences in the Nature of the work according to the variable years of service where there were differences in favor of the years of service less, and the absence of differences in the perception of the employees of the type of The dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of administrative staff depending on the variable level of career (Director, Head of Department, and Administrative Officer).

The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the interest of the departments of the Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip and Al-Aqsa University in particular should be provided with a good Style of Leadership Pattern that encourages the employees to perform well, improve the Nature of the work for administrative staff to serve the interests of work and achieve satisfaction among employees, to give universities the opportunity to participate in decision-making, the need for continuing the departments of universities to pay attention and continuous improvement of the performance of employees, the importance of solving the problems of employees and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems, the use of the staff rotation method periodically, and strengthening the democratic The dominant pattern of leadership and empowering university staff.

Keywords: The dominant pattern of leadership, the nature of the work, administrative staff, Al-Aqsa University, Palestinian universities, Palestine.

1. INTRODUCTION

The human resource is one of the most valuable resources in the institutions, because of the role it plays in the life of these institutions in terms of success, efficiency, survival and growth. In addition, it is the most complex resource as it is subject to many internal and external influences. Human nature makes the response of employees to these influences varied, and therefore their behavior varies accordingly. The studies of human behavior in institutions have received the attention of researchers in management science, through studying the behaviors and attitudes of employees and their performance, and the impact of environmental variables on their behavior, as well as their impact on the performance of the institution and its effectiveness (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2016), (El Talla et al., 2017), (Abu-Naser et al., 2017) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2016).

The human resource, like other resources, needs an administrative leadership capable of utilizing and maintaining these resources, especially on the basis of the various current transformations, characterized by rapid developments and changes in various fields. Administrative leadership is the focus of activities in all institutions. The leader's the dominant pattern of leadership is one of the key factors for the success or failure of an organization. It influences the behaviors of employees in their formal and informal roles (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2016), (El Talla, 2015), (Abu-Naser et al., 2016) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2017).

The behavior of organizational citizenship is informal behavior and is part of the official job description within the organization. It is a voluntary behavior by employees. This behavior is an important factor for the organization to achieve its objectives and develop its competitive advantage. Here it is clear the role of the administrative leader, who must be fully aware of the behavior of his staff in order to

guide them to serve the goals and objectives of the institution (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (El Talla et al., 2018), (Abu-Naser et al., 2018) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2018).

The phenomenon of leadership has been occupied by specialists and researchers. Leadership is one of the most important topics in the life of the institutions that work on developing the competencies of the employees as well as the adoption of strategies and methods to develop and support these skills and abilities. Where leadership is an important focus of the various activities in both public and private institutions. In view of the growing institutions, their size, the complexity of their work, their complexity, the diversity of internal relations, their interconnectedness and their impact on the external environment in the era of rapid technological progress. All of which call for continuing research and continue to bring about change and development, and this task cannot be achieved only under conscious leadership, in order to identify the most important problems facing institutions and provide solutions to them in order to achieve the objectives and objectives of the clients, Its ability to make optimal use of the Foundation's resources and resources in raising performance through the use of effective The dominant pattern of leaderships within the institution skills (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2016), (El Talla et al., 2017), (Abu-Naser et al., 2016) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2016).

In today's world of professional experience and the administrative revolution, the resolution of all kinds and forms of inspiration is no longer an inspiration to the supreme leader at the moment, but it is governed by a number of reasons and circumstances that are known and appreciated by technocrats who are now in charge of planning, direction and management, especially in the economic, industrial and military sectors. Leadership has become an important issue at the top of the corporate and corporate agenda, and senior men of industry are seen as senior leaders who stand side by side in the ranks of top military commanders and top political leaders, taking the names of many university professors and leading academics who shine and become known. Leadership is one of the most important pillars of the armed forces and is the backbone of its importance in human resources management (Sadler, 2008).

Leadership in both the private sector and the public sector is one of the key functions of guidance, development and modernization in the performance of enterprises and an important element in activating the ability of organizations to fulfill their role and achieve their objectives. Leadership behavior and trends are an important indicator of what kind of efforts are being made to improve performance and develop organizations and human resources (Abu Al-Nasr, 2009). The success of the institution in achieving its objectives and mission is related to how the leader manages, The dominant pattern of leadership he exercises, and the successful leadership qualities that are represented in his

personality and his ability to employ his abilities towards constructive work in order to build positive human relations among employees, As well as the other administration, the university administration has received great attention in contemporary societies because of the important role it plays in achieving the goals of the country and society in progress, prosperity and development (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (El Talla et al., 2018), (Abu-Naser et al., 2017) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2017).

The role of leadership in performance management, evaluation and development is a fertile area for study and analysis. Leadership in private organizations and companies is best able to create and introduce real and effective development in the performance of the employees, to the nature of the sector to which they belong and the flexibility, competition and competition that requires constant vigilance and continuous activity. Intelligence and high skills in designing positions and managing what each position needs. Therefore, this task is given sufficient attention and attention. The management and development of performance stems from a genuine self-motivation and an integrated qualification capacity of the responsible leaders in the objectives, questions and hypotheses of the research have been established in the scientific framework through which the knowledge and analysis of the role played by the leaders in the management, monitoring, evaluation and development of human resources, as well as the detection of obstacles and obstacles The performance of the staff and the therapeutic methods used to mitigate the shortage or weakness or lack of performance variables or volatility in addition to knowledge of the leadership skills of managers of horses and the characteristics that distinguish them and the impact of training and education in Development of these leadership skills (Abu Al-Nasr, 2009), (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (El Talla et al., 2018), (Abu-Naser et al., 2017) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2018).

The modern administrative era, with its advanced data and capabilities, does not recognize the unlimited authoritarian role of the top administrative leaders, but we judge these leaders if we say that the things of this world are going according to their will, their will and their decisions. We live in an era of professional and technical experts. They are this bloated segment of administrative leaders, executives and technical advisers who are making the administrative, economic and social decision-making in the developed world (Sadler, 2008).

Universities are a good example of organizations that need a good dominant pattern of leadership in order to improve the performance of their employees so that they can carry out their vital function of society. In this sense, the idea of the present study came as the researchers seek to influence the dominant pattern of leadership on the nature of the work of administrative staff at Al-Aqsa University in Gaza.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Leadership is an important focus of various activities in both public and private organizations. In the light of the growing organizations and their size, and complexity, there is an urgent need for change and appropriate development in a way that ensures continuity and excellence. This is a task that can only be achieved under a conscious management leadership that possesses the leadership skills that enable it to move efforts and channel energies to achieve the best level of achievement (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2016), (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (El Talla et al., 2017), (Abu-Naser et al., 2016) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2017).

Leadership as an influence on others guides their abilities and interests in a direction that ensures that the goals are met. The success of the leader depends primarily on his characteristics and personality traits that determine the type of leadership he exercises to influence his subordinates to improve their performance. It is now clear that the progress of societies and countries is a natural result of the efforts of this responsible and responsible administrative leadership to improve the performance of their members. Those are the most important reasons for obtaining continuous evaluation and proper achievement of goals (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2016), (El Talla et al., 2018), (Abu-Naser et al., 2018) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2018).

There is no doubt that universities are one of the most active institutions of the country through the service of a large segment of society and are accredited in the performance of these services to the efforts of the various departments working in universities, led by The dominant pattern of leaderships that presided over departments and departments in universities , and in view of the great importance of these leaders and their impact on the job performance of the staff of those universities emerged the problem of research is to identify the impact of The dominant pattern of leadership on the nature of the work of administrative staff at Al-Aqsa University - Gaza, where the problem of research in answer to the following questions:

Q1- What is the reality of the dominant pattern of leadership at Al-Aqsa University?

Q2: What is the nature of the work prevailing at Al-Aqsa University?

Q3: Is there an impact of the dominant pattern of leadership on the nature of the work prevailing at Al-Aqsa University?

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Highlighting the dominant pattern of leadership at Al-Aqsa University.
2. Learn about the Nature of the work at Al-Aqsa University.
3. Measuring the impact of the dominant pattern of leadership on the Nature of the work at Al-Aqsa University.

4. To identify differences in the type of leadership and Nature of the work according to the demographic variables (gender, age, qualification).
5. Identify differences in the dominant pattern of leadership and Nature of the work according to functional variables (years of service, job level, and workplace).
6. Providing suggestions and recommendations the management of Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip and all departments working in Field of education helps to improve and improve the performance of employees.

4. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The importance of the study is shown by the benefit that will be given to:

1. It may help the management of Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip to identify the dimensions of the relationship between the dominant pattern of leadership and the Nature of the work in universities to create the appropriate organizational climate to improve the work.
2. University leaders know the appropriate the dominant pattern of leadership to deal with employees to improve their performance.
3. It dealt with an important subject of organizational behavior, and its vital role in influencing many other variables within the university related to individuals.
4. Because universities are affected by the quality and effectiveness of their human resources, and an important part of these resources is administrative staff, so more attention should be paid to them so that they can achieve their goals and objectives.
5. Enriching the library with studies related to this field.

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

In order to provide an appropriate answer to the questions posed, and the study seeks to test the validity of the following assumptions:

H01: There is a statistically significant impact of the dominant pattern of leadership in the university on the nature of the work of its administrative staff.

H02: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the respondents in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the demographic variables (gender - age - scientific qualification).

It has the following sub-assumptions:

H02-1: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the sample members in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the gender variable.

H02-2: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the respondents in the prevailing leadership pattern and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the variable age.

H02-3: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the respondents in the dominant pattern of

leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the variable of scientific qualification.

H03: There are statistically significant differences in the opinion of the respondents in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the organizational variables (years of service - job level).

It has the following sub-assumptions:

H03-1: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the sample members in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the variable years of service.

H03-2: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the respondents in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the variable of the functional level.

6. RESEARCH VARIABLES:

- **Independent variables:** The dominant pattern of leadership
- **Dependent variable:** Nature of the work
- **Demographic and Organizational Variables** (Gender, Age, Academic Qualification, Years of Service, Career Level)

7. RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

1. **Human Limit:** This study is limited to the responses of administrative staff.
2. **Institutional limitation:** The study was conducted at Al-Aqsa University.
3. **Time Limits:** This study was implemented at the beginning of 2018 and therefore represents the reality at this time.

8. RESEARCH TERMINOLOGY

The dominant pattern of leadership: Leadership and supervision patterns are key factors in determining the nature of the organizational climate. Leadership and its patterns have a significant impact on the dynamics of the community and the activity of the organization, in creating the human interaction necessary to achieve the goals of the individual and the organization. The essence of the process of leadership lies in the individual's own abilities through which he influences the behavior and feelings of a group of other individuals (Hamoud, 2002).

Nature of the work: The Nature of the work is an important factor in motivating or discouraging employees. Routine work leads to boredom, neglect, apathy, and indifference to the adoption of modernization or development. The employee often feels that his work is not important. It encourages employees to contribute their full potentials and creative energies to the development of their potentials and potentials for successful work and achievement of goals (Hamoud, 2002).

9. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Study of (Ahmed et al., 2018) aimed to examine the Information Technology used and its effect on the nature of the work of the administrators at Al-Azhar University in Gaza. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire randomly distributed among the employees of Al-Azhar University in Gaza. The study was conducted on a sample of 77 employees the response rate was 92.20%. The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high degree of Information Technology Used at Al-Azhar University- Gaza from the point of view of the administrative staff, where the percentage (74.14%). And that there is a high level of the prevailing Nature of Administrators Work from the point of view of administrative staff, where the percentage (72.14%), there is a direct correlation between the Information Technology Used and the Nature of Administrators Work, there is a statistically significant effect of the Information Technology Used on the Nature of Administrators Work at the university, the absence of differences between the sample according to the variable (gender and variable age) in their perception of the Information Technology Used and the Nature of Administrators Work, there are differences of statistical Sig. in the perception depending on the variable of scientific qualification in Field of the Nature of Administrators Work, while there were no differences in Field: technology used, the differences in the Nature of Administrators Work according to the scientific qualification were in favor of those who obtained the diploma degree compared to postgraduate studies, the absence of differences in the perception of employees of the Information Technology Used and the Nature of Administrators Work according to the variable years of service, and the variable level of employment (manager, head of department, administrative officer), and the change of the workplace. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is the necessity of giving universities the opportunity to participate in decision-making, the continued administration of universities interest and continuous improvement of the performance of its employees, the need to strengthen the periodic evaluation of job performance and to inform the employees and to express their opinion, the importance of solving the problems of Employees and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems, the need to use the method of rotation of employees and periodically, and the importance of strengthening the democratic the dominant pattern of leadership and empowering university staff.
- Study of (FarajAllah et al., 2018) aimed to know the relationship between the nature of the work and the type of communication among the Employees in the

Palestinian universities. A comparative study between Al-Azhar University and Al-Aqsa University. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire that is randomly distributed among the employees of Al-Azhar and Al-Aqsa universities in Gaza Strip. The study was conducted on a sample of (176) administrative employees from the surveyed universities. The response rate was (85.79%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high degree of satisfaction with the nature of work prevailing in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip from the point of view of the administrative staff, where the percentage was (68.15%). There is a Mean level of communication from the point of view of administrative staff, with a percentage of (67.50%). There is a direct correlation between the nature of the work and the prevailing pattern of communication. There is an absence of differences between the sample according to the gender variable in their perception of the nature of work and the prevailing pattern of communication. There is an absence of differences in the perception of Employees nature of work and the pattern of communication prevailing depending on the variables (age, years of service, job level, and university). There are statistically significant differences between Al-Azhar University and Al-Aqsa University in favor of Al-Azhar University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the interest of the management of the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip in general, and Al-Aqsa and Al-Azhar Universities in particular should be provided with a good nature of work and communication. There is a need for continuing the management of universities to pay attention and continuous improvement of the performance of employees. There is an importance of solving the problems of Employees and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems. Staff rotation should be used periodically and the need to strengthen the democratic the dominant pattern of leadership and empower university Employees.

- Study of (Madi et al., 2018) aimed to identify The Organizational Structure and its impact on the dominant pattern of leadership in the Palestinian university in Gaza Strip. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire randomly distributed among Palestinian university Employees in Gaza Strip. The study was conducted on a sample of (320) administrative staff from the three universities. The required sample calculated according to the law (274) Employees, and the response rate was (81.87%). The study found that there is a high degree of satisfaction with the nature of The Organizational Structure in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip from the point of view of the administrative staff, which reached (68.05%). The results showed that there was a

Mean level of participation of decision-makers, with a percentage of (64.91%). There is a direct correlation between the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision makers. There is a significant impact of The Organizational Structure on the participation of decision makers. There is absence of differences between the sample according to the gender variable in their perception of the nature of The Organizational Structure and the extent of participation of decision-makers. There is absence of differences in the perception of Employees to the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision-making Employees depending on the age variable. There are statistically Sig. differences according to the variable of scientific qualification in The Organizational Structure, while there were no differences in the extent of participation of decision-making personnel. And the absence of differences in the perception of the Employees of the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision-making staff according to the variable years of service, the variable level of employment (manager, head of department, administrative officer), the variable of the workplace, and there are differences in the perception of the Employees of the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision-making personnel depending on the university in which they work in all areas. And that there are significant differences between the Islamic University and Al-Azhar University in The Organizational Structure, the extent of the participation of decision-making personnel, in favor of the Islamic University. And that there are statistically significant differences between Al-Azhar University and Al-Aqsa University in the extent of the participation of decision makers in favor of Al-Azhar University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the management of the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip in general, and the Al-Aqsa and Al-Azhar Universities should be particularly interested in providing an appropriate and flexible The Organizational Structure. There is a need for the universities to have the opportunity for Employees to participate in decision-making, the importance of continuing the managements of the universities interest and continuous improvement of the performance of its Employees, the need to solve the problems of Employees and give them the opportunity to contribute to solve their own problems, the use of the staff rotation method periodically, and strengthening the democratic the dominant pattern of leadership and empowering university staff.

- Study of (Almasri et al., 2018) aimed to study The Organizational Structure and its role in applying the Information Technology Used the Palestinian universities as a comparative study between Al-Azhar

and Islamic universities. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire that randomly distributed among Palestinian university workers in Gaza Strip. A sample of (182) administrative staff from the two universities, the response rate was (81.35%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high level of the Information Technology Used from the perspective of administrative staff, there is a direct correlation between The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used, the role and impact of The Organizational Structure in the nature of the Information Technology Used, the absence of differences between the sample according to the variable (gender and age), there are statistically significant differences in the perception of The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used according to the variable of scientific qualification in The Organizational Structure, while there were no differences in Field of the Information Technology Used, the differences in The Organizational Structure according to the scientific qualification were in favor of those who obtained the diploma degree compared to other practical qualifications, the absence of differences in the perception of employees The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used depending on the variable years of service, the differences in The Organizational Structure and technology perception depending on the job level variable (Director, Head of Section, and Administrative Officer) for the benefit of the Administrative Officer, the absence of differences in the perception of employees The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used depending on the workplace variable, the differences in the perception of employees The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used by the University working for the Islamic University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the managements of the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip should be given more attention to the existing The Organizational Structure and modified to suit the need of work, the need for universities to continue to pay attention to the continuous improvement of the Information Technology Used and strengthening the democratic the dominant pattern of leadership and empowering university staff.

- Study of (Abu Sultan et al., 2018) aimed to identify the type of leadership and its role in determining the type of administrative communication at the Islamic University. The researchers used the method of Stratified random sampling in the study. The study was conducted on a sample of 144 administrative staff from the Islamic University of Gaza. The response rate was 77.08%. The study found that there is a high degree of satisfaction with The Style of Leadership in the Islamic University -

Gaza from the point of view of the administrative staff, where the percentage reached (73.52%). There is a high degree of satisfaction with the pattern of communication prevailing in the Islamic University- Gaza from the point of view of administrative staff, where the percentage (76.52%). There is a direct correlation between The Style of Leadership and communication pattern, the role of The Style of Leadership in determining the type of administrative communication at the Islamic University- Gaza. There are no differences in the perception of workers in the pattern of communication while there are differences in The Style of Leadership according to the age variable in favor of the lower age groups. There are no statistically significant differences in the perception of the leadership pattern according to the variable (gender, qualification) and the absence of differences in the perception of the employees of The Style of Leadership and style of communication depending on the variable years of service, and the absence of differences in the perception of the employees of The Style of Leadership and style of communication depending on the level of career variable (manager, head of department, administrative officer). The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the interest of the departments of the Palestinian universities and the Islamic University should be increased in order to provide and maintain a good The Style of Leadership, the need to improve the existing communication pattern at the university and to give universities the opportunity to participate in decision-making, the importance of solving the problems of workers and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems. The need to use the method of rotation of employees and periodically, and the importance of promoting democratic leadership and empowerment of university staff.

- Study of (Al Shobaki et al., 2018) aimed to identify the performance of the administrative staff in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire distributed randomly to the sample of 320 administrative staff from the three universities. The response rate was (81.87%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high level of performance from the point of view of the administrative staff, as the percentage reached (81.51%). The results showed that there were no differences in the perception of the employees according to the variables "age, years of service, job level (manager, head of department, administrative, and place of work)". The results showed that there are differences in the perception of employees to perform the function depending on the university variable, where the results indicated that there are statistically significant differences between the Islamic University and Al-Aqsa

University in the job performance in favor of the Islamic University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the managements of the three Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip should give special attention to job performance in general and Al-Aqsa University and Al-Azhar University in particular. The Employees of universities should have the opportunity to participate in decision-making. The Management of the three universities should keep interest in continuous improvement of the performance of their employees. Enhancing the periodic evaluation of the job performance, informing employees about their evaluations, and giving them the chance to express their opinion about it. Solving employees' problems and giving them the opportunity to contribute in solving their own problems. And the use of the staff rotation method periodically.

- Study of (El Talla et al., 2017) aimed to investigate the relationship between the organizational variables and job performance at Gaza strip Universities, the organizational variables included: communication style, Nature of the work, the technology used. And it aimed to identify the extent of differences statistically significant in employees trends toward the reality of organizational variables attributed to some characteristics of the study population. The data has been collecting using a questionnaire consisting of (50) paragraphs. The questionnaire was distributed randomly to (320) employees of the administrative staff in Gaza strip universities; (262) employees responded, and the results showed the availability of a high degree of organizational variables in Gaza Universities, the order of variables were as follows: the technology used, the Nature of the work, and finally communication style, and it showed a high level of job performance, in addition the results showed a significant correlation between organizational variables and job performance, and there was existence of differences in the perception of the organizational variables depending on the university, for the benefit of the Islamic university, and differences between AlAzhar University and Alaqsa University for the benefit of Al-Azhar University, as results showed no differences between the sample depending on the variables: the functional level and the workplace.
- Study of (El Talla, 2015) aimed to investigate the reality of the burnout among Gaza electricity distribution company employees, which included burnout dimensions: Emotional exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Personal accomplishment. And aimed to the organizational causes of burnout, and it aimed to identify the extent of differences statistically significant trends in working toward the reality of burnout attributed to some demographic and organizational characteristics of the study population. The data has

been collecting using a Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) consisting of (22) items. And the questionnaire of organizational causes of burnout consisting of (31) items. The questionnaires were distributed randomly to (69) employee, the results showed that the availability of a medium degree of burnout in the company, and that there is high availability of Emotional exhaustion scope, average degree for Depersonalization scope and low degree of Personal accomplishment scope. Also the results showed the existence of organizational causes for burnout among employees with the exception of the area of social relations, which was moderately and was the order of the causes are as follows (the weakness of physical stimulation, the limited powers of the work, work stress, conflict of values, poor social relationships). The results showed no differences between the samples due to the variables of gender, age, and years of service in their perception of burnout. The researcher recommended the company to work on treatment the causes of burnout, and increase the attention to employees.

- Study of (Ammar, 2015) which aimed to study the effect of the administrative leadership on the performance of the employees in the economic institution. The study of the case of the Sonlegaz Institution, the distribution directorate, to test the relationship between administrative leadership and a single dependent variable is the job performance. The study concluded that the most important results were a positive relationship of statistical significance between the prevailing supervision pattern (the democratic pattern) and the high level of job performance. And the existence of a positive relationship of statistical significance between the construction of teams and the level of performance of the job. And the existence of a positive relationship with statistical significance between motivation and high level of functional performance. There are statistically significant differences in the attitudes of the respondents on the administrative leadership on the performance of the job according to the demographic variables. The study concluded with recommendations that most importantly suggest that managers and administrators maintain the democratic style of leadership. And proposes to reduce the rigor in the application of instructions and orders strictly, and a soft approach to dealing. And believes that the administrative leadership to achieve integration of the system of incentives, both material and moral.
- Study of (El Talla, 2014) aimed to investigate the reality of the organizational climate for administrator's staff at Al-Azhar University - Gaza, which included some elements of the organizational climate such as: organizational structure, the dominant pattern of leadership and the extent of participation of employees in decision-making. It aimed to identify the extent of differences statistically significant trends in working

toward the reality of organizational climate attributed to some demographic and organizational characteristics of the study population. The data has been collecting using a questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed at random-layer sample to (77) male and female employees of the administrative staff in the university; The results showed that the availability of a medium degree of organizational climate at the Al-Azhar University with percentage (66.64 %), and that there is availability of the average for all scopes of organizational climate, with the exception of The dominant pattern of leadership which its degree was high. The orders of scopes were as the following: The dominant pattern of leadership , the organizational structure , and finally the extent of participation of employees in decision-making The results showed no differences between the samples due to the variables of gender, age, years of service in their perception of organizational climate, while there are significant differences in the perception of the reality of organizational climate depending on the variable qualification in the areas of (organizational structure, the extent of participation in decision-making and in the total scope of organizational climate); and that differences were in favor of holding a diploma, the differences did not exist in the scope The dominant pattern of leadership .

- A study (Jassim and Hammoud, 2011) aimed at discovering the relationship between the elements of the organizational climate and the management of the university performance through the development of a number of main hypotheses, which states that there is a relationship of significant effect for all elements of the organizational climate in the management of university performance. A sample of (50) faculty members at the University of Muthanna. The study found that there is a relationship between the organizational climate and the management of the university performance, where it was found that there is a relationship of the effect of the elements of the organizational climate in the management of the university performance except the variable participation in decision-making. While the change in the dominant pattern of leadership has the highest level of agreement. The study recommended that the university administration take care of the organizational climate by paying attention to its available elements and not available in the work environment in order to improve performance.
- Study of (Hassan, 2010) which aimed to identify the dominant pattern of leaderships in Palestinian NGOs, identify their job performance, and also identify the nature of the relationship between The dominant pattern of leaderships and job performance in Palestinian NGOs. The impact of organizational variables on the employees' estimates of the dominant the dominant pattern of leadership and its impact on job performance.

The study was conducted on 138 NGOs (340 managers, heads of departments and others). The study concluded that the democratic The dominant pattern of leadership is the most widely used in Palestinian NGOs, followed by the autocratic The dominant pattern of leadership and the latest free style. The results showed that the overall level of job performance was good. The study showed a statistically significant correlation between the democratic the dominant pattern of leadership used in Palestinian NGOs and the level of job performance, and the existence of a statistically significant inverse relationship between the democratic leadership pattern employed by Palestinian NGOs and the level of job performance in these organizations. The study concluded the recommendations, the most important of which is the need for the directors of the NGO to explain and clarify the vision of the organization and its values and goals for the subordinates

- A study of (Bahr and Abu Swirih, 2010) aimed of the study was to identify the extent of statistical differences in the attitudes of employees towards the effect of the elements of the organizational climate on the functional performance due to the demographic characteristics of the members of the study society. The study was conducted using a questionnaire consisting of (80) items, which were distributed randomly to (215) employees and administrative staff of the university, and it was possible to collect 180 valid questionnaires for analysis. The study found that there is a positive organizational climate in the Islamic University and a strong positive relationship between the availability of a good organizational environment and the level of job performance of the Islamic University employees. There is a very good level of job performance for the employees of the Islamic University and there are no statistically significant differences in opinions of individuals the sample on the degree of influence of the elements of the organizational climate on the performance of the administrative staff is due to gender, age, scientific qualification and place of work.
- Study of (Al-Hunaiti, 2010) Aimed at determining the impact of The dominant pattern of leaderships on the performance of government agencies in Jordan, determining The dominant pattern of leaderships prevailing among managers in government agencies, and determining the level of job performance in government agencies in Jordan. The study population consists of 335 directors and directors of government departments. The study concluded with the most important results that there is an impact of the dominant pattern of leaderships of managers on the performance of the functions in government agencies in Jordan. There is an impact of leadership patterns (transformational, autocratic and democratic) on managers' performance. There is no impact of the leadership (exchange, anarchist) patterns of managers on

career performance. There were no statistically significant differences in the effect of the dominant pattern of leaderships on the performance of the managers due to the variables (gender, age, academic qualification and functional experience). The study concluded with recommendations, the most important of which is the need to prepare training programs for both leaders and employees of government agencies. And the distribution of brochures and booklets containing management literature on the concept of the dominant pattern of leaderships and theories to help managers to choose the appropriate the dominant pattern of leadership to deal with subordinates to achieve the best level of administrative performance.

- Study of (Al-Aga, 2010) Which aims to identify the role of administrative leaders in the development and change and organizational positive in the banks operating in the Gaza Strip and identify patterns of leadership (democracy, bureaucracy, free) in the development and positive organizational change at the level of individuals and groups and organization itself. The research community consists of senior and middle managers and administrators in public banks, which have 630 employees and employees. The study concluded that the predominant pattern in the Palestinian banks was the democratic pattern followed by the bureaucratic leadership followed by the free dominant pattern of leadership. The study concluded with the results of the most important of which is the strengthening of the democratic orientation of leaders in banks operating in the Gaza Strip. And increasing interest in developing leadership capabilities in banks through training, preparation and good qualification of leaders.
- Study of (Al-Shanti, 2006) Which aimed to identify the extent of the impact of the organizational climate dimensions prevailing in the ministries of the Palestinian National Authority on the performance of human resources, and the assessment of the organizational climate in these ministries as well as to identify the level of performance of human resources. The results of the study were the most important: the attitudes of the sample towards the prevailing organizational climate positive trends, the positive impact of the organizational climate prevailing in the Palestinian ministries on the performance of human resources and that this climate leads to improved performance. It also showed that there is a defect in the organizational structure of the ministries and the methods and methods of decision-making and the disproportionate nature, functions and duties of the jobs occupied by the employees with the scientific qualifications and disciplines obtained.
- Study of (Al-Sakran, 2004) the aim of this study was to identify the attitudes of the security sector towards the prevailing organizational climate in this sector and the relation to their performance. One of the most important findings of this study was the high positive attitudes of

SS officers towards work systems and procedures. The presence of positive trends high among the officers of the security forces towards administrative communication as one of the axes of the organizational climate affecting the improvement of the performance of the job. 3 - The existence of positive trends high among private security officers towards the axis of "employee perception of his role" as one of the axes of performance. The study recommended the following: The need for the attention of officials in the private security forces sector to the components and elements of the organizational climate. And to ensure the development and rehabilitation of the intellectual capacity of all employees in the private security forces. The motivation of the employees of the private security forces sector by supporting them with more material and moral incentives.

- Study of (Hawamdeh, 2003) The aim was to identify the perceptions of the educational leaders of the prevailing organizational climate in the directorates of education in Jordan, and the level of their administrative creativity, in addition to defining the correlation between the organizational climate and the level of administrative creativity. The study sample consisted of (264) educational leaders in Jordan. The results of the study showed that the perceptions of the educational leaders of the organizational climate prevailing in their directorates, positive perceptions, and that there is a positive relationship between organizational climate and managerial creativity.

10. RELATED WORK

First - The dominant pattern of leadership:

The attitude theory and its models of leadership behavior were beginning to shift towards leadership thinking. Attention was clearly shown in an effective the dominant pattern of leadership, and this was associated with changing attitudes of individuals. The research began from the framework of personality traits and the dominant pattern of leadership towards the role of subordinates and the community and the ability of the leader to adapt to it. On the other hand, to meet the requirements of modern management and administrative effectiveness, new trends of leadership have emerged and this study is meant to show the details of each the dominant pattern of leadership separately (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (Al Shobaki et al., 2017).

An effective the dominant pattern of leadership plays an essential role in achieving the objectives efficiently and effectively. The administrative leadership, which adopts a humanitarian philosophy based on participation in decisions and policies and procedures. Which will enhance confidence in the employees and stimulate the state of organizational loyalty and create the dimensions of psychological stability (Al Shobaki et al., 2018).

Humanity has become known to the administration since the life of the group has become complicated. People's roles

have been multiplied. Cooperation between individuals and groups has become an important demand. It is necessary to increase their effectiveness in achieving the better life of society through the good investment of natural resources on the one hand and the achievement of security, stability and development on the other. (Kanaan, 1980).

Leadership is a social role played by an individual while interacting with other members of the group. This role is characterized by having the power and ability to influence others and direct their behavior towards the goal of the group and leadership is a form of social interaction between the leader and followers where leadership and dependency are highlighted. Leadership represents the leader's behavior to help achieve the group's goals, move the group towards goals, improve social interaction among members, maintain community cohesion, and facilitate resources for the group (Al Shobaki et al., 2018).

Leadership is defined as "the process of influencing subordinates", including dictatorships or autocracies characterized by centralism, authoritarianism, punishment, low-level communication or one-way approach, limiting the exchange of views, ideas, participation, creativity, and democratic leadership. Power, communication in both directions, and reward, which encourages interaction and the presentation of creative ideas and creativity (Al-Emian, 2005).

The essence of the process of leadership lies in the individual's self-abilities through which he influences the behavior and feelings of a group of other individuals. In his leadership role, the leader has the ability to influence others and guide their behavior towards achieving the goals. The organizational climate, which has meaningful leadership abilities, others towards effective performance (Hamoud, 2002).

Although the creativity of leaders themselves helps create and create new products, services and methods for the organization, the most important is to make their subordinates imitate them in creativity, because the creation of new products, services and tools is more effective at the level of individuals and employees in production lines than in senior management (Jad Al-rab, 2013). In order to improve performance and organized innovation, leaders can follow the following steps (Jad Al-rab, 2008):

- Provide high levels of expertise.
- Focus on intrinsic motivation to perform tasks.
- Eliminate the restrictions on subordinates.
- Shorten and reduce the evaluation process of solutions provided.
- Provide a brainstorming atmosphere.
- Support the ability of the community to bear the risk of creative thinking.

Administrative Leadership Patterns

The leadership can be divided into several modes according to the criteria that determine the classification. From the

point of view of effectiveness, the leadership can be divided into positive and negative leadership. On the one hand, authority can be divided into centralize and decentralized leadership (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (El Talla et al., 2018), (Abu-Naser et al., 2018) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2018). In terms of the nature of the organization, it can be divided into official and informal leadership. Most studies agree on dividing the leadership into three main types: leadership Democratic, autocratic and a third liberal. The following is a brief description of these patterns:

▪ **Democratic The dominant pattern of leadership (participatory style, positive style, constructive style or orientation)**

This leadership is based on three pillars: human relations, participation and delegation of authority. The democratic leadership is based on trust in the principals, taking advantage of their opinions and ideas, allowing their initiative to plan their work, and developing the prospects for cooperation between the employees (Yaghi, 1996). It fosters the morale of employees, doubles production capacity, encourages entrepreneurship, develops creativity and innovation, and satisfies the human, economic and psychological needs of employees (Kanaan, 1980). A democratic leader often does not hold power in currency, but rather interacts with subordinates, informing them of the problems they face, taking their decisions and engaging them in making decisions.

▪ **Autocratic The dominant pattern of leadership: (dictatorial-authoritarian)**

The autocratic leadership revolves around a single axis: the subordination of all things in the organization to the authority of the leader who leads the organization. He informs the presiding officers and hears and obeys without their discussion, and the passive stimulus is often used (Yaghi, 1996). This pattern is based on the assumption that a lazy man tends to evade responsibility and lack of work, and this is a form of criticism and reliance on others, and makes him work out of fear of punishment and punishment rather than love for work (Al-Nemr et al., 1997).

▪ **Leadership or pattern: (chaotic - non-wave - absolute - free - solubility)**

This pattern is an overarching model of the democratic pattern, and the leader is working as follows (Asaad, 2005):

1. The leader loses the elements of effective leadership due to the abandonment of responsibility in making decisions.
2. The commander provides information to members of his group and leaves them free to identify without any interference from it.
3. Gives the commander the greatest degree of freedom and the full freedom of members in decision-making without making an effective contribution.

4. The communication between the leader and the members shall be limited as narrow as possible.
5. The group does not respect its leader in the belief that its leader is weak.

Second- Nature of the work:

Routine work leads to boredom, neglect, indifference and indifference towards modernization and development, because creativity is discouraged and the individual feels that his work is not important (Al-Emian, 2005).

The nature of the work greatly affects the performance. The more the Nature of the work encourages innovation and creativity, the better the performance, the greater the efficiency and the efficiency of the employees, and the more the Nature of the work is routine, the more frustrated the employees. Therefore, organizations should constantly work on the Nature of the work commensurate with the qualifications and abilities of the people who are based on it, by putting the right person in the right place, in addition to the periodic rotation of employees in different jobs to kill the spirit of monotony at work, and increase their experience and improve their performance, And to inform them of the importance of the functions and roles they play, and the extent to which this function contributes to the overall productivity of the Organization (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (El Talla et al., 2017), (Abu-Naser et al., 2018) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2017).

Third- Al-Aqsa University, Gaza

Al-Aqsa University began in 1955 as a teacher's institute under the direction of the Egyptian government. The goal was to prepare and rehabilitate teachers. In 1991, the Institute developed into a faculty known as the Faculty of State Education. Since then, the College has gradually grown in its educational plans, its scientific departments, its professors and its students. Many teachers and researchers with high academic and educational qualifications have graduated from BA, with the University of Ain Shams and with the beginning of the academic year 2000/2001 the college was transferred to Al-Aqsa University. The number of administrative staff at Al-Aqsa University is 298 Employee.

Administrative staff in Palestinian universities is an essential component of the organizational structure of Palestinian universities. Without these employees, universities cannot perform their great mission of serving the community through their teaching services, research and continuing education. This work is not completed without

Table 1: The distribution of respondents according to variables: level of employment, gender, age, academic qualification, years of service, place of work

Career Level	Director	Head Of The Department	Administrative Employee	Total	
	7	6	67		80
Gender	Male	Female		80	
	56	24			
Age	20-30 years	31-40 years	41-50 years	Greater than 50 years	80
	40	31	9	0	

administrative staff. In Fields of student affairs, admission and registration, finance, public relations, personnel affairs, maintenance, procurement, warehousing, services and security, and other administrative functions (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2016), (El Talla et al., 2018), (Abu-Naser et al., 2018) and (Abu Amuna et al., 2018).

11. ANALYTICAL APPROACH

First- Methodology of the study:

This study deals with the study of tools, phenomena and practices existing and available for study and measurement as they are, without the intervention of researchers in their course, and researchers can interact with them and describe them and analyze them scientifically and objectively the study will rely on two basic types of data:

1. **Initial Data:** The study was carried out in Field by distributing questionnaires to study the vocabulary of the study and to collect and compile the necessary information in the subject of the study, and then unloading and analyzing it using the statistical program and using the appropriate statistical SPSS tests in order to arrive at indications of value and indicators that support the subject of the study.
2. **Secondary data:** Through the review of books and periodicals, special publications and scientific and professional journals related to the subject of the study, and any references contribute to enrich the study in a scientific way, and the researchers through the use of secondary sources in the study to identify the foundations and methods of scientific studies in writing studies, Recent developments have occurred in Field of study.

Second- Study Population:

The study population consists of all administrative staff at Al-Aqsa University in the Gaza Strip and through the census of the study society, it was found that it consists of (298) administrative staff.

Third- The study sample:

- A. A survey sample was used by the researchers to verify the validity and reliability of these tools. The sample size was 32 administrative staff.
- B. The random stratified sample method was used in the study. The study was conducted on a sample of (99) administrative staff. The response rate was (80.80%).

Qualification	Diploma	BA	Postgraduate	80	
	18	56	6		
Years of service	Less than 5 years	5-7 years	8-10 years	More than 10 years	80
	33	20	17	10	

Fourthly- Study tool:

Since the nature of the hypotheses and the variables involved are the ones that control the choice of the appropriate tool, accordingly, the researchers have prepared a measure for that study commensurate with its objectives and hypotheses, a measure of the impact of the dominant pattern of leadership on the Nature of the work in universities. The process of designing and preparing the study scale has gone through several stages and steps:

- The goal was to design the scale to be applied to administrative staff at Al-Aqsa University to obtain data for analysis and interpretation to answer the study's questions.
- Researchers have identified the concept of The dominant pattern of leadership in institutions of higher

education, through the literature on the subject, and previous studies,

The researchers drafted the scale items taking into account the following:

- Suitable scale for administrative staff (respondents).
- Clarity of meaning and lack of ambiguity.
- His linguistic integrity.

Scale units:

The final scale included 20 words distributed across the two fields (The dominant pattern of leadership and Nature of the work)

How to correct the meter:

The five-dimensional Likert scale was used to measure respondents' responses to the questionnaire sections according to the following table

Table 2: Scale of the five-dimensional Likert scale

Response	Strongly Disagree	disagree	neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Degree	1	2	3	4	5

Each question has five answers (strongly disagree - disagree - neutral – agree - strongly agree), asking the respondent to read each question or answer with an ✓ sign in proportion to his or her vision of reality, (Strongly Agree) Five points, (agree) four points, (neutral) three points, (disagree) two points, and (strongly disagree) one point, so that the relative weight in the last case is 20% and is proportional to this response.

Believe the meter: The researchers calculated the validity of the meter in the following ways:

1. **Authentic honesty:** Researchers have verified the authenticity of the tool ostensibly by presenting to a group of holders of a doctorate degree in business administration, and the apparent honesty shows the general appearance of the test in terms of relevance to

the examinees, and the affiliation of the phrase to Field, and clarity of wording and instructions.

2. **Authenticity of internal consistency:** The internal consistency coefficient is a correlation coefficient between each unit of scale and the whole scale, so this method is usually used to determine the veracity of the test on the one hand and the viability of its units on the other. The researchers calculated the validity of the internal consistency of the scale by finding the correlation coefficients between each field and the total score of the scale. The researchers conducted a survey sample of 32 Employees by finding correlation coefficients for each paragraph in Field to which they belong, as well as correlation coefficients between each field And the scale as a whole, as in the following tables:

Table 3: Honesty coefficients for each paragraph with the total score of the driving style field

No.	Item	Honesty level	Level of Sig.
1.	The dominant pattern of leadership of the university helps them to progress and progress.	0.643	0.01
2.	Managers' decisions are clear.	0.829	0.01
3.	Managers encourages thoughtful change.	0.805	0.01
4.	Direct supervisor allows staff to participate in decision-making related to their work.	0.761	0.01
5.	Direct supervisor work to motivate employees and encourage them to change, innovate and innovate.	0.773	0.01
6.	Management provides me with the necessary support to do my work and the duties required of me.	0.696	0.01
7.	There is trust and cooperation between the direct and subordinates	0.788	0.01
8.	The direct supervisor encourages his/her subordinates to express their views and suggestions.	0.835	0.01
9.	My direct supervisor shows great interest in my wishes.	0.807	0.01

No.	Item	Honesty level	Level of Sig.
10.	I am encouraged by my direct supervisor to solve my own business problems.	0.744	0.01

Table 4: Honesty coefficients for each paragraph with the total grade of the Nature of the work

No.	Item	Honesty level	Level of Sig.
1.	Working hours and working days are appropriate.	0.563	0.01
2.	Office designs provide psychological and physical comfort (ventilation, lighting, movement).	0.381	0.05
3.	Management provides security and safety features.	0.366	0.05
4.	Let me work many opportunities for innovation and innovation	0.604	0.01
5.	The size of the work is consistent with my personal abilities and my scientific qualifications.	0.640	0.01
6.	My work requirements are consistent with my abilities and skills.	0.692	0.01
7.	I am satisfied with the duties and tasks at work.	0.591	0.01
8.	My job gives me appreciation and respect for others in society	0.715	0.01
9.	University employees enjoy the holidays they are entitled to according to the system.	0.535	0.01
10.	My job provides stability and job security.	0.457	0.01

Stability of the scale:

The concept of stability means the ability of the test to give the same grades or values to the same individual or individuals if the measurement process is repeated. To ensure the stability of the scale, the researchers used the following methods:

1. **Method of split half:** by calculating the correlation coefficient between the individual questions and marital questions, and obtained the stability coefficients shown in the following table.

Table 5: Stability coefficient of the scale

No.	Field	No. of Items	Correlation Coefficient Before Adjustment	Correlation Coefficient After Adjustment	Level of Sig.
1.	The dominant pattern of leadership	10	0.763	0.866	Significant at (0.01)
2.	The Nature of the Work	10	0.565	0.722	Significant at (0.01)

From the above table, it is clear that the stability coefficients in all midterm segments were high, indicating that the questionnaire has a high degree of stability.

2. **Coefficient of alpha- Cronbach stability of persistence:** The researchers used the Coefficient of alpha- Cronbach stability coefficient to calculate the stability coefficient for all the terms of the scale, where the general correlation coefficient (0.862) is a high stability coefficient indicating the strength and validity

of the scale. The researchers noted that the results of Pearson correlation coefficients are consistent with the results of Coefficient of alpha- Cronbach stability, and then the researchers performed the coefficients of Coefficient of alpha- Cronbach stability between the terms of each field separately and is shown in the following table:

Table 6: Shows the coefficients of Coefficient of alpha- Cronbach stability for each dimension of the scale

No.	FIELD	COEFFICIENT OF ALPHA- CRONBACH STABILITY
1.	The dominant pattern of leadership	0.919
2.	The Nature of the Work	0.731

The above table shows that all Coefficient of alpha- Cronbach stability are above (0.731). This indicates that the questionnaire has a high degree of stability.

Fifth- Statistical Methods:

The computer was used in the statistical processing, especially the statistical packages program (SPSS), where all the data obtained by the researchers and then the results were

extracted through the scientific equations necessary for this and the most important used in this study:

1. Averages, frequencies, standard deviations and percentages.
2. Spearman Brown’s correlation coefficient for the equal half - division, and the Cronbach alpha factor to determine the stability of the resolution.

3. Pearson correlation coefficient to measure the relationship between variables.
4. T test to find the differences between the averages.
5. Analysis of mono-variance to see differences between more than two groups.
6. Scheffe post-test to measure the direction of differences.

Answer the study questions:

Table 7: Scale of measurements used in this study

THE LEVEL METHOD	VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
SMA	Less than (1.80)	From (1.80): (2.59)	From (2.60): (3.39)	From (3.40):(4.19)	Greater than(4.20)
RELATIVE WEIGHT	Less than 36.00%	From 36.00: 51.90%	From 52.00: 67.90%	From 68.00: 83.90%	Greater than 84.00%

This indicates that the Means of less than 1.80 indicate a very low degree in the elements of Field. The Means of (1.80: 2.59) indicate a low degree of availability of field elements, (2.60: 3.39) indicate that there is a medium degree in the elements of Field, and the Means ranging from (3.40: 4.19) indicate that there is a large degree in the elements of

Q1-: What is the reality of the dominant pattern of leadership at Al-Aqsa University?

To answer the study questions and to use the pentagram in the study instrument, the study adopted the criterion mentioned by Abdul Fattah (2008) to judge the trend when using the pentagram. The following table illustrates this:

Field. More than (4.20) indicate that there is a very large degree in the elements of Field on the scale used in the study shown in the previous table.

To answer this question, the researchers resorted to repetitions, averages, standard deviation, percentages and order. The results were as shown in the following tables:

Table 8: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentages and Ranking of Responses of Sample Members in the Field of Leadership Pattern

No.	ITEM	TOTAL SCORES	MEAN (5)	STANDARD DEVIATION	PERCENTAGE	RANK
1.	The dominant pattern of leadership of the university helps them to progress and progress.	243	3.04	1.277	60.80%	2.8
3.	Managers' decisions are clear.	274	3.43	1.123	68.60%	4.1
5.	Managers encourages thoughtful change.	259	3.24	1.094	64.80%	3
6.	Direct supervisor allows staff to participate in decision-making related to their work.	256	3.20	1.267	64.00%	7
7.	My direct supervisor works to motivate employees and encourage them to change, innovate and innovate.	237	2.96	1.237	59.20%	9
8.	Management provides me with the necessary support to do my work and the duties required of me.	226	2.83	1.178	56.60%	10
9.	There is trust and cooperation between the direct and subordinates.	257	3.29	1.229	65.80%	2
10.	The direct supervisor encourages his/her subordinates to express their views and suggestions.	259	3.24	1.172	64.80%	4
11.	My direct supervisor shows great interest in my wishes.	242	3.03	1.273	60.60%	5
12.	I am encouraged by my direct supervisor to solve my own business problems.	257	3.21	1.219	64.20%	6
All items of the dimension		251.70	3.1463	.964460	62.93%	

The above table shows the results obtained in Field of The dominant pattern of leadership by presenting the arithmetical averages of Fields of Field. The averages were between (2.83 and 3.43).

We note from the previous table that all the paragraphs range from a medium to a high percentage. One paragraph in this field has a high percentage between (68%) and (83.90%). Nine paragraphs have a medium score between (52.00%) and (67.90%), the paragraph (the decisions of managers are

clear) received the highest percentage (68.60%) followed by the paragraph (there is trust and cooperation between the direct supervisor and subordinates) in second place with percentage (65.80%), then the paragraph (managers encouraging studied changes) ranked third with a percentage (64.80%), the paragraph (the administration provides me with the necessary support to do my work and the duties required of me) came last with a percentage (56.60%), and the total score for Field was (62.93%) which is average

grade. This finding indicates that university staff are moderately satisfied with the dominant pattern of leadership of these universities and the degree of cooperation and trust between leaders and subordinates.

This result differs from the results of Bahr and Abu Swirih (2010) with a high degree of satisfaction with the dominant pattern of leadership. There is also trust and cooperation between the leadership and the staff at the university, and the

Table 9: Frequency, Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentages and Ranking of Responses of Sample Members in the Field of Nature of Work

No.	ITEM	TOTAL SCORES	MEAN (5)	STANDARD DEVIATION	PERCENTAGE	RANK
1.	Working hours and working days are appropriate.	234	2.93	1.240	58.60%	8
2.	Office designs provide psychological and physical comfort (ventilation, lighting, movement).	236	2.95	1.146	59.00%	7
3.	Management provides security and safety features.	252	3.19	1.099	63.80%	6
4.	Work gives me opportunities for innovation and innovation.	228	2.89	1.000	57.80%	10
5.	The size of the work is consistent with my personal abilities and my scientific qualifications.	269	3.45	1.028	69.00%	3
6.	My work requirements are consistent with my abilities and skills.	278	3.48	1.067	69.60%	2
7.	I am satisfied with the duties and tasks at work.	264	3.30	1.118	66.00%	5
8.	My job gives me appreciation and respect for others in society.	303	3.79	0.990	75.80%	1
9.	University employees enjoy the holidays they are entitled to according to the system.	273	3.41	1.110	68.20%	4
10.	My job provides stability and job security.	233	2.91	1.333	58.20%	9
All items of the dimension		258.39	3.2299	.708920	64.60%	

The above table shows the results reached in Field of the Nature of the work by presenting the arithmetic averages of Fields of Field. It is noted that the averages ranged from 2.89 to 3.79.

The above table shows that all the paragraphs ranged from medium to high. There were four vertebrates in this area with a high percentage between 68% and 83.90%. Six were intermediate between 52.00% and 67.90%. The paragraph (giving me the job of esteem and respect for others in the community) has received the highest percentage (75.80%), followed by the paragraph (my work requirements correspond to my abilities and skills) ranked second with a percentage (69.60%), then the paragraph (commensurate with the size of the work) With my personal abilities and scientific qualifications) ranked third and in percentage (69.00%), the paragraph (allows me to work many opportunities for renewal and innovation) in the brotherly rank with percentage (57.80%), and got the total score of Field on a percentage (64.60%), a medium degree.

The results differ with the study of Bahr and Abu Swirih (2010), where the nature of the work at the university gives its employees respect and appreciation in the community and the size of the work corresponds to personal abilities and

university also has a supportive leadership that encourages subordinates to express their views, make suggestions and respond to subordinate proposals. The result was a study (Jassim and Hammoud, 2011) which showed that the driving style was the highest.

Q2: What is the nature of the work prevailing at Al-Aqsa University?

scientific qualifications and provides stability and job security for employees. The results also differed with the study of Al-Sakran (2004), which showed a positive attitude towards the Nature of the work. The researchers attribute this agreement to the general atmosphere of these institutions, the suitable work environment, and the excellent performance of employees. (Al-Shanti, 2006). The results of his study showed that the nature of the work and the duties of the jobs occupied by the employees are not consistent with the scientific qualifications and the disciplines they have obtained. The researchers explain this finding that there is a defect in the organizational structure in the ministries of the Palestinian National Authority.

12. HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H01: There is a statistically significant impact of the dominant pattern of leadership in the university on the nature of the work of its administrative staff.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, the researchers used the linear regression test as shown in the following table:

Table 10: Model Summary

MODEL SUMMARY				
MODEL	R	R SQUARE	ADJUSTED R SQUARE	STD. ERROR OF THE ESTIMATE
1	.375a	.141	.130	.66133
a. Predictors: (Constant), The dominant pattern of leadership				

Table 11: Analysis of variance by ANOVA test

ANOVA						
MODEL	SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	LEVEL OF SIG.	
1	Regression	5.589	1	5.589	12.779	.001b
	Residual	34.113	78	.437		
	Total	39.703	79			
a. Dependent Variable: the Nature of the Work						
b. Predictors: (Constant), The dominant pattern of leadership						

Table 12: Transaction table

COEFFICIENTS						
MODEL		UNSTANDARDIZED COEFFICIENTS		STANDARDIZED COEFFICIENTS	T	LEVEL OF SIG.
		B	STD. ERROR	BETA		
1	(Constant)	2.362	.254		9.310	.000
	The dominant pattern of leadership	.276	.077	.375	3.575	.001
a. Dependent Variable: the Nature of the Work						

From the results described in the previous tables, the following can be inferred:

- There is a statistically significant correlation between the driving style and the Nature of the work at the university.
- Correlation coefficient = 0.375, and the adjusted limiting factor = 0.141, which means that 14.1% of the change in the prevailing Nature of the work was explained by the linear relationship with The dominant pattern of leadership in the university and the remaining percentage may be due to other factors
- The value of the calculated F test is 12.779, and the probability value is 0.001, which means rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the existence of a statistically significant effect between the prevailing

driving style and the Nature of the work at the university.

H02: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the respondents in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the demographic variables (gender - age - scientific qualification).

It has the following sub-assumptions:

H02-1: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the sample members in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the gender variable.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, the researchers used the T-test as shown in the following table:

Table 13: Mean and standard deviations and the value of "T" for the scale domains according to the gender variable

FIELD	GENDER	THE NUMBER	AVERAGE	STANDARD DEVIATION	"T" VALUE	LEVEL OF SIG.
The dominant pattern of leadership	Male	56	3.1054	0.99357	-0.577	0.566
	Female	24	3.2417	0.90598		
The Nature of the Work	Male	56	3.3105	0.69792	1.569	0.121
	Female	24	3.0417	.713180		

It is clear from the previous table that there are no statistically significant differences due to the gender variable between males and females in all fields. The calculated value of T is less than the tabular value of T, which proves the validity of the hypothesis.

The absence of differences between males and females can be explained in terms of the similarities between university leadership with males and females alike, and the lack of discrimination between males and females in the Nature of the work.

H02-2: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the respondents in the prevailing leadership pattern and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the variable age.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

Table 14: The source of the variance, the sum of squares, the degrees of freedom, the mean squares, the value of "P", and the level of significance attributed to the variable of age

FIELD	SOURCE	TOTAL SQUARES	DEGREES OF FREEDOM	AVERAGE SQUARES	"P" VALUE	LEVEL OF SIG.
The dominant pattern of leadership	Between Groups	3.287	2	1.643	1.803	0.172
	Within Groups	70.198	77	0.912		
	Total	73.485	79			
The Nature of the Work	Between Groups	1.973	2	0.986	2.013	0.141
	Within Groups	37.730	77	0.490		
	Total	39.703	79			

It is clear from the previous table that there are no statistically significant differences in these fields and the overall score is due to the age variable of the respondents. The value of the calculated F is less than the value of the table.

H02-3: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the respondents in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the variable of scientific qualification.

This result can be explained by the fact that employees of all ages live in the same organizational environment, are influenced by the same pattern of leadership and live in the same way as the university.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

Table 15: The source of the variance, the sum of the squares, the degrees of freedom, the mean squares, the value of "P", and the level of significance due to the variable of scientific degree

FIELD	SOURCE	TOTAL SQUARES	DEGREES OF FREEDOM	AVERAGE SQUARES	"P" VALUE	LEVEL OF SIG.
The dominant pattern of leadership	Between Groups	3.648	2	1.824	2.011	0.141
	Within Groups	69.837	77	0.907		
	Total	73.485	79			
The Nature of the Work	Between Groups	0.466	2	0.233	0.457	0.635
	Within Groups	39.237	77	0.510		
	Total	39.703	79			

It is clear from the previous table that there are no statistically significant differences in all fields according to their scientific qualifications, since the value of F is less than the value of the F. The result can be explained by the fact that the employees of different scientific qualifications are looking for a good dominant pattern of leadership, and provide the appropriate working nature, and this proves the validity of the hypothesis in a manner.

leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the organizational variables (years of service - job level).

It has the following sub-assumptions:

H03: There are statistically significant differences in the opinion of the respondents in the dominant pattern of

H03-1: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the sample members in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the variable years of service.

Table 16: Source of variance, sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean squares, F value and level of significance due to variable years of service

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

FIELD	SOURCE	TOTAL SQUARES	DEGREES OF FREEDOM	AVERAGE SQUARES	"F" VALUE	LEVEL OF SIG.
The dominant pattern of leadership	Between Groups	3.567	3	1.189	1.292	0.283
	Within Groups	69.918	76	0.920		

FIELD	SOURCE	TOTAL SQUARES	DEGREES OF FREEDOM	AVERAGE SQUARES	“F” VALUE	LEVEL OF SIG.
	Total	73.485	79			
The Nature of the Work	Between Groups	6.194	3	2.065	4.682	0.005
	Within Groups	33.509	76	0.441		
	Total	39.703	79			

It is clear from the previous table that the value of the calculated F is less than the F value of the table. Consequently, there are no statistically significant differences in the dominant pattern of leadership, whereas in

Field of the Nature of the work and there are statistically significant differences, due to variable years of service. To find out the direction of differences in the Nature of the work, the Scheffe Test was used as in the following table:

Table 17: Results of the Scheffe Test to identify the direction and significance of differences in the nature of work due to the variable years of service

YEARS OF SERVICE	LESS THAN 5 YEARS	5-7 YEARS	8-10 YEARS	MORE THAN 10 YEARS
Less than 5 years	-			
5-7 years	0.027155	-		
8-10 years	*0.594316-	*0.621471-	-	
More than 10 years	*0.547845-	*0.575000-	0.046471	-

* Sig. at 0.05

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at (0.05) due to the variable years of service in Field of "Nature of the work" between the years of service (less than 5 years) and (5-7 years) with holders of years of service (8-10 years) and (more than 10 years) for the benefit of those with less years of service. The researchers explain this finding that those with less service years are in

the career development stage and are often satisfied with the nature of their work, their work,

H03-2: There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the respondents in the dominant pattern of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff due to the variable of the functional level.

To determine the validity of this hypothesis, one way anova was used as shown in the following table:

Table 18: Source of variance, sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean squares, F value, and significance level

FIELD	SOURCE	TOTAL SQUARES	DEGREES OF FREEDOM	AVERAGE SQUARES	“F” VALUE	LEVEL OF SIG.
The dominant pattern of leadership	Between Groups	0.255	2	0.128	0.134	0.875
	Within Groups	73.230	77	0.951		
	Total	73.485	79			
The Nature of the Work	Between Groups	1.413	2	0.707	1.421	0.248
	Within Groups	38.289	77	0.497		
	Total	39.703	79			

The above table shows that the calculated F is less than the F value of the table, meaning that there are no statistically significant differences in all fields according to the functional level variable, which proves the hypothesis is incorrect.

The researchers explain this result that employees at different levels of employment have the same view of the dominant pattern of leadership and Nature of the work as the sample consists of administrative staff, who often receive the top instructions and policies from the University Council and composed of academics.

13. RESULTS

- The results showed that there is a moderate degree of the dominant pattern of leadership at Al-Aqsa University

from the point of view of administrative staff, with a percentage of (62.93%).

- The results showed that there was an average level of satisfaction with the nature of the work from the point of view of the administrative staff, where the percentage reached (64.60%).
- The results showed that there is a direct correlation between the dominant pattern of leadership and the Nature of the work.
- The results showed a statistically significant effect of the dominant pattern of leadership on the Nature of the work.
- The results showed that there were no differences between the sample in the view of the type of leadership

and the Nature of the work according to the gender variable.

- The results showed that there were no differences in the perception of the dominant pattern of leadership and the Nature of the work according to the age variable.
- The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the view of the type of leadership and the Nature of the work according to the variable of scientific qualification.
- The results indicated that there were no differences in the perception of The dominant pattern of leadership according to the variable years of service
- The differences in Field of Nature of the work according to the variable years of service where there were differences in favor of years of service less.
- The results indicate that there are no differences in the employees' perception of the type of leadership and the nature of the work of the administrative staff according to the change in the career level (manager, head of department, administrative officer).

14. RECOMMENDATIONS

- The interest of the departments of the Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip and the University of Al-Aqsa should be increased in particular to provide a good dominant pattern of leadership that encourages the employees to perform well.
- Improve the nature of the work of the administrative staff to serve the interests of the work and achieve satisfaction among the employees.
- Provide universities with the opportunity to participate in decision-making.
- University administrations continue to pay attention to and continuously improve the performance of their employees.
- Solve employee problems and give them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems.
- Use the staff rotation method periodically.
- Strengthening the democratic the dominant pattern of leadership and empowering university staff.

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